
Editing Guidelines

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Table of Contents

Metadata	1
Title	3
Editors and collaborators	4
Funding	4
Edition	5
Publication and licence	5
Textual source	6
Description of the document	7
Author	8
Creation place	8
Creation date	9
Language	9
Abstract	9
Categories	10
Text	10
Textual structure	10
Authorial interventions	13
Editorial interventions	15
Letters	19
Sender, recipient, places and dates	19
Postal address	20
Beginning of the letter	21
Writing sessions	21
Closing of the letter	21
Postscript	22

Metadata

The descriptive metadata used in Proyecto Humboldt Digital identify the following:

- the digital edition,
- the editors and publishers,
- the source from which the text is derived,
- the conditions related to the creation
- the text type by categories.

This metadata has been applied to all types of text (documents, letters, etc.).

The structure of a TEI header of a generic document is as follows:

```
<teiHeader>  
    <fileDesc>
```

```

<titleStmt>
  <title type="main">[Enter data]</title>
  <funder ref="https://www.auswaertiges-amt.de/de/">
    Auswärtiges Amt</funder>
  <funder ref="https://www.fritz-thyssen-stiftung.de/">
    Fritz Thyssen Stiftung</funder>
  <funder ref="https://www.gerda-henkel-stiftung.de/">
    Gerda Henkel Stiftung</funder>
  <editor>
    <persName>
      <surname>[Enter data]</surname>
      <forename>[Enter data]</forename>
    </persName>
  </editor>
</titleStmt>
<editionStmt>
  <p>Dossier Digital: Alexander von Humboldt y Cuba (1800-1830).
  ProHD (<date>2022-2023</date>)</p>
</editionStmt>
<publicationStmt>
  <publisher>Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie
  der Wissenschaften</publisher>
  <publisher>Oficina del Historiador de la Ciudad
  de la Habana</publisher>
  <pubPlace>Berlín</pubPlace>
  <pubPlace>La Habana</pubPlace>
  <availability status="free">
  <licence target="http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/">
    Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0)</licence>
  </availability>
</publicationStmt>
<sourceDesc>
  <msDesc rend="manuscript">
    <msIdentifier>
      <institution>[Enter data]</institution>
      <collection>[Enter data]</collection>
      <idno>
        <idno type="shelfmark">[Enter data]</idno>
        <idno type="uri">[Enter data]</idno>
      </idno>
    </msIdentifier>
    <physDesc><p>[Enter data]</p></physDesc>
  </msDesc>
</sourceDesc>
</fileDesc>
<profileDesc>
  <creation>[Enter data]</creation>
  <langUsage>
    <language ident="">[Enter data]</language>
  </langUsage>
  <abstract xml:lang="es">
    <p>[Enter data]</p>
  </abstract>
  <abstract xml:lang="de">
    <p>[Enter data]</p>
  </abstract>
  <textClass>
    <catRef></catRef>

```

```

    </textClass>
  </profileDesc>
  <encodingDesc>
    <classDecl>
      <taxonomy xml:id="pb-taxonomy">
        <category xml:id="genre">
          <category xml:id="correspondence"/>
          <category xml:id="diaries"/>
          <category xml:id="essays"/>
          <category xml:id="notebooks"/>
          <category xml:id="travelwriting"/>
        </category>
        <category xml:id="form">
          <category xml:id="manuscript"/>
          <category xml:id="print"/>
        </category>
        <category xml:id="subjects">
          <category xml:id="administration"/>
          <category xml:id="climatology"/>
          <category xml:id="coffee"/>
          <category xml:id="colonialism"/>
          <category xml:id="demography"/>
          <category xml:id="economicconditions"/>
          <category xml:id="education"/>
          <category xml:id="emancipation"/>
          <category xml:id="factories"/>
          <category xml:id="geography"/>
          <category xml:id="medicine"/>
          <category xml:id="plantations"/>
          <category xml:id="science"/>
          <category xml:id="scientificexpedition"/>
          <category xml:id="sugar"/>
          <category xml:id="slavery"/>
          <category xml:id="tobacco"/>
          <category xml:id="trade"/>
        </category>
      </taxonomy>
    </classDecl>
  </encodingDesc>
</teiHeader>

```

Title

All editions have been identified with a main title. The title has been orthographically standardised.

In titleStmt, the encoding of the main title has been done using the title element and the type="main" attribute. For example:

```
<title type="main">Carta de consulta al Ayuntamiento
de La Habana</title>
```

After the main title, the title in another language, with the original spelling, an alternative title or a subtitle is optionally included. For this purpose the title element can be repeated below the main title together with the attribute @type="sub":

```
<title type="main">Carta de Francisco de Arango y Parreño
a Alexander von Humboldt</title>
<title type="sub" xml:lang="fr">À Monsieur Mr. le Baron
A. Humboldt</title>
```

The `@xml:lang` attribute has been optionally used with a standard code to indicate the language of the alternative title: "es" for Spanish, "fr" for French, "de" for German, "en" for English, etc.

Editors and collaborators

In the `titleStmt`, the editors have been identified with the `editor` element. The name of the person has been encoded with the element `persName` as it follows:

- Surname: `surname`
- Forename: `forename`

An external database in the form of a URL, e.g. VIAF or ORCID, has been optionally encoded in the `@ref` attribute.

```
<editor>
  <persName ref="http://viaf.org/viaf/21973914">
    <surname>[Surname]</surname>
    <forename>[Forename]</forename>
  </persName>
</editor>
```

If there is more than one editor, the `editor` element has been repeated. For example:

```
<editor>
  <persName>
    <surname>Tylus</surname>
    <forename>Piotr</forename>
  </persName>
</editor>
<editor>
  <persName>
    <surname>Kraller</surname>
    <forename>Kathrin</forename>
  </persName>
</editor>
```

If other people have been involved in the edition with minor tasks, the name of the contributors has been included with the element `respStmt` (statement of responsibility). Again, the name of the person has been added in the element `persName`. In the `@ref` attribute, the reference to an external database such as VIAF or ORCID has also been optionally encoded in the form of a URL.

The type of collaboration has been defined in detail with the `resp` (responsibility) element. In a `note` element the type of contribution has been defined using the following values: collaboration, editorial collaboration, transcription, commentary or records. For example:

```
<respStmt>
  <persName ref="http://viaf.org/viaf/21973914">
    <surname>[Apellido]</surname>
    <forename>[Nombre]</forename>
  </persName>
  <resp>
    <note type="remarkResponsibility">Collaboration</note>
  </resp>
</respStmt>
```

Funding

After the name of the publisher, the three funding bodies have been identified: Auswärtiges Amt, Fritz Thyssen Stiftung and Gerda Henkel Stiftung.

In titleStmt the funder element has been used as follows:

```
<funder ref="https://www.auswaertiges-amt.de/de/">
  Auswärtiges Amt
</funder>
<funder ref="https://www.fritz-thyssen-stiftung.de/">
  Fritz Thyssen Stiftung
</funder>
<funder ref="https://www.gerda-henkel-stiftung.de/">
  Gerda Henkel Stiftung
</funder>
```

The funder element contains the @ref attribute with the URL of the website of the three funding bodies.

Edition

All editions of the project mention the Proyecto Humboldt Digital and document the edition date. This edition information has been encoded with the editionStmt and p elements as follows:

```
<editionStmt>
  <p>Proyecto Humboldt Digital ( <date>2021</date> )</p>
</editionStmt>
```

The date in brackets corresponds to the year of creation of the TEI document; it is important not to confuse this date with the date of creation of the source.

Publication and licence

Information on the organisations responsible for the distribution and publication of the editions, the places of publication and the licence has been encoded in all editions.

For this purpose, the publicationStmt element has been used. Within this element, three nested elements have been used:

- publisher (publishing entity),
- pubPlace (publication place),
- availability (availability).

For example:

```
<publicationStmt>
  <publisher>
    <ref target="http://www.bbaw.de">Berlin-Brandenburgische
      Akademie der Wissenschaften (BBAW)</ref>
  </publisher>
  <publisher>Oficina del Historiador de la Ciudad de la Habana</publisher>
  <pubPlace>Berlín</pubPlace>
  <pubPlace>La Habana</pubPlace>
  <availability status="free">
    <licence target="http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/">
      Creative Commons Atribución
      4.0 Internacional (CC BY 4.0) </licence>
    </availability>
</publicationStmt>
```

Optionally, the information on the entity responsible for the publication has been enriched using the ref element to provide a hyperlink to the website with the @target attribute. Also, optionally, the

@ref attribute has been used in the pubPlace element to identify the place of publication with a URI from GeoNames.

The publisher and pubPlace elements are repeatable, i.e. it is possible to include more than one entity and place of publication, but the information on the availability of the file is not repeatable. Thus, the availability element, with a @status="free" attribute, contains a licence element with information about the licence of the digital edition; the @target attribute has been used to give the URL of the licence.

In all the editions of the project, the licence "Creative Commons Atribución 4.0 Internacional (CC BY 4.0)" has been used.

Textual source

In all editions of the project, the source from which the text is derived, the name of the institution where the document is held and at least one identifier such as a shelfmark have been encoded.

The source description has been encoded with the msDesc (manuscript description) element. Inside, the msIdentifier element provides information about the institution holding the document with the institution element and the shelfmark with the idno element, which contains the @type attribute with the value shelfmark. This idno element has been encoded inside another idno element in order to repeat as many idno elements as necessary. Optionally, information about the collection has been included with the collection element and the name or title of the source as it appears in the document using the msName element. For example:

```
<msDesc type="copy">
  <msIdentifier>
    <institution>[institution]</institution>
    <collection>[collection]</collection>
    <idno>
      <idno type="shelfmark">[shelfmark]</idno>
    </idno>
    <msName>[name or title of the document]</msName>
  </msIdentifier>
</msDesc>
```

Tip

It is important not to confuse the name or title of the source encoded in msName with the title of the digital edition, which may differ.

When the source is a printed document or a printed edition has been consulted, the information has been encoded in witness within listWit. Inside, a bibl element has been used to encode a bibliographic reference using the attribute @type with the value print to distinguish it from a manuscript.

For example:

```
<witness>
  <bibl type="print">Humboldt, Alexander von: Geografía de la plantas,
    ó Quadro físico de los Andes Equinoxiales, y de los países
    vecinos. Semanario del Nuevo Reyno de Granada...</bibl>
</witness>
```

URI identifier of the bibliographic record

Document sources are traditionally identified by a shelfmark or another type of identifier. Since the shelfmark can only be partially identified by machines, a URI (Uniform Resource Identifier) has been added whenever possible, if known or available. The identifier is standardised and machine-readable, as it only consists of certain characters and symbols (e.g. blanks are not allowed).

Wherever possible, a URI has been used to link the edited text to the bibliographic record in the project's digital repository.

Element	Insertion place	Attribute	Content
idno	// msIdentifier/id- no/idno	@type="uri"	[URI]

The idno element has been used as part of the msIdentifier element and as a child element of another idno using the @type attribute with value "uri" for permalinks or "URLImages" for facsimiles. For example:

```
<idno>
  <idno type="shelfmark">Caja pequeña 7b, no. 68</idno>
  <idno type="uri">http://kalliope-verbund.info/DE-611-HS-1272345</idno>
  <idno type="URLImages">
    http://resolver.staatsbibliothek-berlin.de/SBB00015CC500000000</idno>
</idno>
```

Type of textual source

The source from which the edited text is derived can be of different types:

- Manuscript
- Copy
- Draft
- Print

Where more than one textual source is used, a **single document** has been selected as the textual basis. The other textual witnesses have been explicitly mentioned in the edition only where they convey variants by means of an editorial comment.

If the existence and content of a document has been deduced with the help of other documents, there is no textual basis. In this case, in the msDesc element, the textual source type has been encoded with the @rend attribute. The following values have been chosen for this purpose:

Value of @rend	Type of source
notExtant	Elaborated
concept	Draft
manuscript	Manuscript
copy	Copy
Print	print

For example:

```
<msDesc rend="manuscript">
```

Description of the document

The physical characteristics (paper, format, number of pages, etc.) of the textual source have been optionally described.

The description of the document has been encoded with the `physDesc` (physical description) element. The description is encoded as text in a `p` element:

```
<physDesc>
  <p>Manuscrito autógrafa de autor desconocido en buen estado
  de conservación y de seis páginas de extensión. Forma parte del
  documento conocido como &quot;Umschlag mit den Materialien für die
  Statistik von Kuba [Werk]&quot;. Doble numeración: una paginación
  original en tinta; otra moderna en lápiz que solo numera los
  folios (123-124). Contiene algunas adiciones en tinta negra
  al inicio del documento, en los márgenes y al final del texto en
  francés por Alexander von Humboldt.</p>
</physDesc>
```

Author

If the author of the text is known, this information has been encoded in the `profileDesc` element. There, a `creation` element has been added to provide metadata about the author, place of writing and date of creation.

The author's name has been encoded with the `persName` element. For example:

```
<profileDesc>
  <creation>
    <persName>Arango y Parreño, Francisco de (1765-1837)</persName>
  </creation>
</profileDesc>
```

The following order has always been observed: first the surname and then the first name, separated by a comma. If the date of birth and death is known, it has been included followed by the first name and in brackets as shown in the example above.

When the author is unknown, the same `persName` element has been used, but with the content "N/A" (Not Available). For example:

```
<creation>
  <persName>N/A</persName>
  <persName key="H0012069">Humboldt, Alexander von (1769-1859)</persName>
  <date when="1804-04-10">10 de abril de 1804</date>
  <placeName key="https://www.geonames.org/3553478">La Habana</placeName>
</creation>
```

Whenever more than one person has been involved in the creation of the text, the `persName` element has been repeated.

Creation place

If the place of creation is known, it has also been encoded in the `profileDesc` element. Within `creation`, a `placeName` has been used to encode the name of the place. Optionally, an attribute `@key` has been used to provide an external identifier from Geonames. For example:

```
<placeName key="https://www.geonames.org/3553478">La Habana</placeName>
```

If the place is unknown, the content of `placeName` should be "N/A" (Not Available). For instance:

```
<persName key="H0012069">Humboldt, Alexander von (1769-1859)</persName>
  <date notBefore="1802">No antes de 1802</date>
<placeName>N/A</placeName>
```

In this case, the `@key` attribute has not been used.

Creation date

If the creation date is known, it has been encoded with the `date` element observing the format YYYY-MM-DD (or YYYY-MM or YYYY, depending on the information available) and using the attributes `@when`, `@from/@to` or `@notBefore/@notAfter`. This allows the web application to use this data to search for information in a specific time period or to filter documents based on the standardised date.

- Exact date:

```
<date when="1772-12-21">tres días antes
  de la Nochebuena del año 1772</date>
```

- Time period:

```
<date from="1731-11-11" to="1741-09-11">del 11 de noviembre
  de 1731 al 11 de septiembre de 1741</date>
```

- Approximate time period:

```
<date notBefore="1804-05-01" notAfter="1804-05-16">Primera mitad
  de mayo de 1804</date>
```

In addition, the `@cert` attribute has been optionally used to encode the certainty of the date with the values `high` and `low`.

When the creation date is not known, the `date` element has also been used, but with the value "N/A" (Not available). For example:

```
<persName key="H0012682">Arango y Parreño, Francisco de (1765-1837)</persName>
  <date>N/A</date>
<placeName key="H0006819">La Habana</placeName>
```

Language

In all editions of the project, the main language of the text has been encoded. In `profileDesc`, the `langUsage` element has been used. There, the `language` element has been nested to encode the language. For example:

```
<langUsage>
  <language ident="es">Español</language>
</langUsage>
```

The `@ident` attribute has been used to identify the language with a standardised code: "es" for Spanish, "de" for German, "en" for English, "fr" for French, etc.

If the text contains substantial parts in another language, a `language` element has been repeated to encode the secondary language. For example:

```
<langUsage>
  <language ident="es">Español</language>
  <language ident="fr">Francés</language>
</langUsage>
```

Abstract

In all editions of the project, a summary of the intellectual content of the text, the themes, the ideas discussed, etc. has been provided.

The abstract has been encoded with `profileDesc/abstract` in a `p` element as follows:

```
<abstract xml:lang="es">
  <p>Notas de Humboldt sobre la obra de
  Jean Nicolas Berthe "Précis Historique
  de la Maladie qui a régné dans l'Andalousie en 1800".
  Humboldt resume las tesis del trabajo de Berthe en
  preparación de su tratado científico sobre la fiebre amarilla.
  La obra de Berthe fue publicada en 1802.</p>
</abstract>
```

The abstract has been provided in Spanish and German. The `abstract` element has been repeated and the `@xml:lang` attribute has been used with a standardised two-character code: "es" for Spanish and "de" for German.

Categories

In `profileDesc` the `textClass` element has been used to include different categories to classify the edited text. The categories used are: genre, form and subject(s). For this, the `catRef` element has been used with the attributes `@scheme` and `@target`. For example:

```
<textClass>
  <catRef scheme="#genre" target="#notebooks"/>
  <catRef scheme="#form" target="#manuscript"/>
  <catRef scheme="#subject" target="#slavery"/>
  <catRef scheme="#subject" target="#geography"/>
  <catRef scheme="#subject" target="#sugar"/>
</textClass>
```

The three categories are repeatable and optional. All categories have been previously defined in the project taxonomy located in the `taxonomy` element.

Where possible, terms from the Library of Congress and other national libraries such as the Deutsche Nationalbibliothek and the Biblioteca Nacional de España have been used.

Text

The logical structure of the edited texts have been encoded explicitly. All paragraphs, line breaks, lists, tables, notes and drawings have been explicitly represented with TEI elements. Additional textual phenomena encoded explicitly are the following: the pagination or foliation of the source, including blank pages, and changes in typography such as highlights, spaces left by the author, authorial interventions such as deletions, additions and substitutions, and editorial interventions such as normalisations, resolution of abbreviations, supplied words, corrections of obvious errors, uncertain readings, omissions and words in a foreign language.

Textual structure

Foliation and pagination

In all editions of the project, the start of the foliation or pagination, i.e. the place where a new folio or page starts, has been encoded.

The beginning of the folio or page has always been encoded with the empty element `pb/` (pagebreak). The `@n` attribute contains the page or folio number (depending on the physical sequence of the document or author).

distinta de las demás<pb n="3v"/>colonias del continente Americano

The digitisation of the folio or page has been encoded with the attribute `@facs` (facsimile). The file name of the digital image file includes the archival foliation and the extension "tif". The file name corresponds to a URI, i.e. it is unique in the digital dossier. For example:

```
<pb n="1r" facs="prohd0014_1r.tif"/>
```

Any other numbering or pagination information contained in the source has been encoded with the `fw` (forme work) element; this element carries the `@type` attribute with the value `folNum`:

```
<fw type="folNum">34</fw>
```

Sections and headings

In documents with a relevant internal logical structure, such as minutes and protocols, the sections have been optionally encoded using the `div` element. For example:

```
<tex>
  <div>
    <div>[Sección o apartado 1]</div>
    <div>[Sección o apartado 2]</div>
  </div>
</tex>
```

This internal structure has always been encoded in combination with pagination or foliation with `pb` and the use of `p`.

In such documents section headers have been encoded with the `head` element.

Blank pages

In all editions of the project, the blank pages of the textual source have been encoded explicitly. In addition, a distinction was made between blank pages, missing pages, semantically significant blank spaces and omissions by the editors.

In order to represent and display the foliation correctly, each (blank) page has been encoded individually. Even if there is a succession of blank pages, a number 1 has always been entered for each newly encoded blank page.

Blank pages have been encoded with the (empty) `gap/` element.

```
<pb n="132v"/><gap unit="pages" quantity="1" reason="empty"/>
```

This has been used just after the page break (`pb/`) above. The two attributes `@unit` and `@quantity` of the `gap/` element carry the values `pages` and `1`. The `@reason` attribute contains the value `empty`. When there is more than one blank page in a row, each page has been encoded individually.

Paragraphs

In all editions of the project, paragraphs have been encoded following the sequence of the textual source. Paragraph indentation has been optionally encoded if the editor considers this information relevant.

Paragraphs have been encoded with the element `p` (paragraph).

Line beginnings

Line beginnings have been explicitly encoded following the textual source with an (empty) `lb/` (line beginning) element. The `lb/` element has been used at the **beginning** of the line, as determined by the TEI guidelines.

If a line starts within a word, it has been encoded with the `@break` attribute and the value `no`. If a separator appears in the original source, it has not been transcribed as such but has been encoded with the element `g` and the attribute `@ref="#typoHyphen"`. For example:

```
y le añadí al propio ti<g ref="#typoHyphen"/><lb/>empo
```

Blank spaces

Semantically significant blank space (e.g. authors sometimes leave a space in the text to supplement it later) has been encoded with the empty element `space/`. The reproduction of such gaps in the transcription has been distinguished from omissions made by the editors, as well as from empty or missing pages, each of which has been encoded as `gap/`.

The extent of the omission has been indicated by `@unit` and `@quantity`. If the number of omitted lines (`unit="lines"`), characters (`unit="chars"`) or words (`unit="words"`) cannot be reliably determined, the value `1` has been used in `@quantity`. For example:

```
sur une longueur de plus de <space quantity="1" unit="words"/>. Sa largeur...
```

Optionally, the `@dim` attribute has been used to indicate whether it is horizontal or vertical blank space.

Lists

Lists have been encoded with the `list` element. Each bullet point has been transcribed into an `item` element. Existing numbering has not been encoded independently, but transcribed directly into the `item` element.

```
<list>
  <item>Le Rio Apure près de S. Fernando 206 t.</item>
  <item>Orinoco à la bocca Apure 1905 t.<lb/>
  mais quand le Capucin est islado = 10750 mètres.</item>
  <item>Orinoco près du Baraguan 889 t.</item>
  <item>Orinoco près de urbano 2674 t. <lb/>
  jusqu'au delà de l'Isle de Urba<g ref="#typoHyphen"/>
  <lb break="no"/>na et de I. vieja de Montica.</item>
</list>
```

Tables

The tables contained in the source have been transcribed as such, making a distinction between explicit and implicit tables. Explicit tables are considered to be those drawn by the author, while implicit tables are recognisable only by the arrangement of their contents. A distinction has been made between tables and enumerations that resemble lists.

Tables have been encoded with the `table` element. The first row of the table has been assigned the attribute `@role="label"` to be considered as a header. For example:

```
<table rows="3" cols="2">
  <head>Tabla</head>
  <row role="label">
    <cell>[Header column 1]</cell>
    <cell>[Header column 2]</cell>
  </row>
  <row>
    <cell>[Column 1/ Row 1]</cell>
    <cell>[Column 2/ Row 2]</cell>
  </row> ...
</table>
```

Signatures

Optionally, in documents such as minutes and protocols, the signature of the participants in the session has been encoded in the `closer` element. For this purpose, each signature has been encoded with the element `signed`. For example:

```
<closer>
  <signed> Benigno Duque <choice>
    <orig>deHeredia</orig>
    <reg>de Heredia</reg>
  </choice></signed>
  <signed>Ylincheta</signed>
</closer>
```

Notes

Notes by the author or a contemporary editor have not been inserted following their location in the manuscript, but in the passage of text to which the note actually refers (or which the editor reasonably assumes it refers to).

The notes have been encoded with the `note` element

En los partidos más remotos una caballería
`<note place="mBottom" hand="#author">`La caballería es una superficie de tierra de quatrocientas treinta y dos varas en quadro.`</note>` de tierra montuosa se paga en el día a quinientos pesos fuertes al contado, [...]

Where it is possible to identify the author of the note, this information has been encoded with the `@hand` attribute:

Value	Definition
#author	Author of the text
#addressee	Addressee of this letter
#unknown	Unknown

The place of the note has been encoded with the `@place` attribute:

Value	Definition
left	left margin
right	right margin
mTop	top margin
mBottom	bottom margin
inline	in line

If the author uses an insertion mark, it has been encoded with the empty element `metamark/`. The appearance of the insertion mark (asterisk, number, etc.) has not been made explicit.

A distinction has been made between notes and additions: additions complement the main text and are syntactically integrated into it. Notes are independent text units.

Authorial interventions

In all digital editions of the project, changes in typography and authorial interventions have been encoded explicitly, i.e. with TEI elements.

Highlighted text

Highlighted text marginal marks have been encoded with the `hi` element (highlighted) and the `@rendition` attribute to specify their appearance:

Value of <code>@rendition</code>	Type of highlight
#u	simple
#uu	double
#mMM	marked in the margin

For instance:

Sucinta noticia de la situación
`<hi rendition="#uu">presente de esta colonia. Agosto de 800'</hi>`

If an entire paragraph appears in the highlighted font with a mark in the margin, it has been encoded with the element `p` and the attribute `@rendition` with the value `#mMM` (border mark).

Superscript

Numbers or letters that appear in superscript (i.e. slightly raised above the line) in the text font have been encoded with the element `hi` (highlighted) and the attribute `@rendition` with value `#sup`. For example:

le ofreciera de mi parte
 algunas observaciones `<choice>`
 `<abbr>sob<hi rendition="#sup">e</hi></abbr>`
 `<expan>sobre</expan>`
`</choice>` los `<lb/>` principales hechos

Deletions

As long as it is readable and regardless of whether it is in line beginnings, abbreviations, normalisations and editor corrections or additions, the deleted text has been encoded with the `del` (deletion) element and using the `@rendition` attribute to specify the type of deletion:

Value of <code>@rendition</code>	Type of deletion
#ow	overwritten
#s	strikethrough
#erased	erased

For instance:

Conocen ya estos vecinos la esplendidez en la mesa, las viviendas, muebles, `<del rendition="#s">y` vestidos y tren de calle.

Additions

In all editions of the project, the author's own additions to the textual source have been encoded. In contrast to notes, additions only extend the text and are syntactically integrated.

Additions made by the author have been encoded with `add` (addition) using the `@place` attribute to specify the location of the addition:

Value of <code>@place</code>	Definition
superlinear	above the line
sublinear	below the line

Value of @place	Definition
intraLinear	in line
across	across the text
left	left margin
right	right margin
mTop	top margin
mBottom	bottom margin

For instance:

[...] y logré para el Comercio con extranjeros, los `<add place="intraLinear">ensanches</add>` que se explican en el documento [...]

If there is an insertion mark made by the author in the source, it has been encoded with the `metamark/` element. The form of the insertion mark (asterisk, number, etc.) has not been specified.

Substitutions

If a word or a passage of text is deleted in the source and at the same time a word is added, these two textual phenomena have been encoded together with a `subst` (substitution) element.

The deletion has been encoded with the element `del` (deletion). The type of deletion has been specified in the `@rendition` attribute:

Value	Definition
#ow	overwritten
#s	strikethrough
#erased	erased

The addition has been encoded with the `add` element (addition). The location of the addition has been specified with the attribute `@place`:

Value	Definition
superLinear	above the line
subLinear	below the line
intraLinear	in line
across	across the text
left	left margin
right	right margin
mTop	top margin
mBottom	bottom margin

For instance:

```
<subst>
  <del rendition="#ow">6</del>
  <add place="across">7</add>
</subst>, 4 pesos
```

Editorial interventions

In all digital editions of the project, editorial interventions have been explicitly encoded.

Normalisations

Spelling, punctuation, capitalisation and hyphenation have been explicitly normalised with the `choice` element and its two child elements `orig` (original form) and `reg` (regularised form). In the `orig` element the original form as it appears in the textual source has been encoded while in the `reg` element the regularised form has been encoded, i.e. modernised to the current orthographic norm to facilitate the readability of the text. For example:

```
<choice>
  <orig>espendiendo</orig>
  <reg>expendiendo</reg>
</choice>
```

Whole words have always been encoded even if only one spelling or accent is regularised as shown in the example above.

The same coding method has been followed with the normalisation of the capitalisation:

```
<choice>
  <orig>ensayo</orig>
  <reg>Ensayo</reg>
</choice>
<choice>
  <orig>político</orig>
  <reg>Político</reg>
</choice>
```

The same normalisation method has been applied to contractions or word unions:

```
<choice>
  <orig>dela</orig>
  <reg>de la</reg>
</choice>
```

Abbreviations

Abbreviations have been encoded with the `choice` element and its two child elements `abbr` (abbreviation) and `expan` (resolved abbreviation). In the `abbr` element, the abbreviated form that appears in the textual source has been retained, while in the `expan` element, the editors have provided the resolved or expanded form to facilitate the readability of the text.

```
<choice>
  <abbr>q</abbr>
  <expan>que</expan>
</choice>
```

Acronyms have been encoded as abbreviations following the same method with `choice`.

Supplied words, characters and punctuation

Words, characters or punctuation marks that are clearly missing in the source and have been supplied (that is, added) by the editor have been encoded with the `supplied` element. The `@cert` (certainty) attribute has been used to encode the certainty with which the text has been supplied:

Value	Definition
low	low certainty
high	high certainty

For instance:

30 de julio de `<supplied cert="high">18</supplied>27`

Errors and corrections

Obvious errors appearing in the textual source have been encoded with the element `choice`. Inside, the erroneous word has been encoded with the element `sic` while the correction has been encoded with `corr`. In the `corr` element, the attribute `@cert` (certainty) indicates the certainty of the correction:

Value	Definition
low	low certainty
medium	medium certainty
high	high certainty

For example:

```
<choice>
  <sic>Humboldt</sic>
  <corr cert="high">Humboldt</corr>
</choice>
```

When a word is repeated and it is clear that this is an error, the same `choice` element has been used to encode the erroneous word with `sic`. However, in these cases a corrected form has not been provided but the `corr` element has been used and left empty. In addition, the `type` attribute with value "deleted" has been used to indicate that a redundant word has been removed. For example:

```
<choice>
  <sic>más</sic>
  <corr type="deleted"/>
</choice> cantidad
```

Unclear text

Words or passages that are not easily readable have been encoded with the `unclear` element. The `@reason` attribute has been used to specify the reason for the unclear reading:

Value	Reason
illegible	unclear text
covered	unclear to read because of strikethrough

With the attribute `@cert` (certainty) the certainty of the intervention has been encoded.

Value	Definition
low	low certainty
high	high certainty

For instance:

```
<unclear reason="illegible" cert="high">año</unclear>
```

Illegibility

Illegible characters or words in the textual source due to material damage or unclear writing have been encoded with the empty element `gap/`.

The `@reason` attribute has been used to indicate the reason for illegibility:

Value of @reason	Reason
lost	destruction or lost
illegible	illegible
covered	unclear to read because of strikethrough

If the number of lines, words, etc. are known, they have been encoded using @unit and @quantity.

Value of @unit	Illegible unit
chars	characters
lines	lines
pages	pages
words	words

In the @quantity attribute, the number of unreadable characters, lines, etc. has been encoded.

```
<gap reason="illegible" unit="words" quantity="3"/>
```

If a character (or string of characters) is strikethrough and cannot be read, it has been encoded with both del and gap/:

```
<del rendition="#s">
  <gap reason="illegible" unit="chars" quantity="5"/>
</del>
```

Finally, destroyed or missing pages have also been encoded individually.

```
<pb n="1r"/><gap reason="lost" unit="pages" quantity="1"/>
```

Omissions

Omissions have been explicitly encoded. Omissions of characters, words, text passages or whole pages by editors and publishers have been encoded with the empty element gap/. The @unit attribute specifies the type of unit taken into account by the editor:

Value of @unit	Illegible unit
chars	characters
lines	lines
pages	pages
words	words

With the @quantity attribute, the number of characters, lines, etc. omitted has been encoded while with the @reason attribute the reason for the editorial omission has been encoded.

Value of @reason	Reason
fm	text in foreign language
insignificant	unimportant text for the corpus

For instance:

```
a menudo <gap unit="words" quantity="1" reason="fm"/> entonces de nuevo
```

In order to correctly represent and display the foliation, each page has been encoded individually. Even if several consecutive pages are omitted, the omission is always encoded with a 1 as the number corresponding to each missing page.

Comments

The editorial comments have been encoded with the element `seg` (arbitrary segment). In turn, two elements have been nested: on the one hand, `orig` with which the commented textual passage has been encoded; on the other hand, `note` with which the editorial comment itself has been encoded. The `@type` attribute has been used in `seg` with the value `comment`.

```
<seg type="comment">
  <orig>plantarum</orig>
  <note>Se refiere a "De distributione geographica plantarum secundum
    coeli temperiem et altitudinem montium".</note>
</seg>
```

Dates

The dates appearing in the textual source have been encoded with `date`. To make the dates computer-readable, the format YYYY-MM-DD has been followed in the attributes `@when`, `@from` and `@to`, as well as `@notBefore` and `@notAfter`.

- Exact date:

```
<date when="1772-12-21">tres días antes
  de la Nochebuena del año 1772</date>
```

- Time period:

```
<date from="1731-11-11" to="1741-09-11">del 11 de noviembre
  de 1731 al 11 de septiembre de 1741</date>
```

- Approximate time period:

```
<date notBefore="1804-05-01" notAfter="1804-05-16">Primera mitad
  de mayo de 1804</date>
```

In addition, optionally, the `@cert` attribute with the values `high` and `low` has been used to encode the certainty with which the date is known to be correct.

Letters

In this project, letters have received special treatment due to their characteristic features. In terms of metadata, where possible, the sender, recipient, place and date of sending and receiving have been encoded. As far as the structure is concerned, where present in the source, the postal address, the beginning of the letter, the acts of writing (if there were interruptions) and the closing of the letter have been encoded.

Sender, recipient, places and dates

The metadata relating to the correspondence of a letter has been encoded in the element `correspDesc` (correspondence description). A `correspAction` (correspondence action) element has been created for the sending and receiving process respectively. The `@type` attribute has been used to specify the type of the communication action; two values are allowed: `sent` or `received`.

```
<correspDesc>
  <correspAction type="sent">[Sender]</correspAction>
  <correspAction type="received">[Recipient]</correspAction>
</correspDesc>
```

Within the `correspAction` element, the elements `persName`, `orgName`, `placeName` and `date` have been used to identify the person or organisation involved in the exchange, the place where

it happens and the date. Wherever possible, information on persons, organisations and places has been linked to the identifier encoded in the @key attribute. This information can be indicated for all named entities.

```
<correspDesc>
  <correspAction type="sent">
    <persName key="H0012682">Arango y Parreño, Francisco de</persName>
    <placeName key="H0006819">La Habana</placeName>
    <date when="1827-07-30">30 de julio de 1827</date>
  </correspAction>
  <correspAction type="received">
    <persName key="H0012069">Humboldt, Alexander von </persName>
  </correspAction>
</correspDesc>
```

Dates have been encoded with the date element following the format YYYY-MM-DD (or YYYY-MM or YYYY, depending on the information available) in the attributes @when, @from/@to or @notBefore/@notAfter. In addition, in the @cert attribute, the values high and low have been used to indicate the certainty about the date. For example:

- Exact date:

```
<date when="1772-12-21">tres días antes de
la Nochebuena del año 1772</date>
```

- Exact time period:

```
<date from="1731-11-11" to="1741-09-11">del 11 de noviembre de
1731 al 11 de septiembre de 1741</date>
```

- Approximate period:

```
<date notBefore="1804-05-01" notAfter="1804-05-16">Primera mitad
de mayo de 1804</date>
```

When it has not been possible to determine the sender, the addressee or the places and dates of sending or receiving, the corresponding elements have been used, but with the value "N/A" (Not Available). For example:

```
<correspDesc>
  <correspAction type="sent">
    <persName key="H0012069">Humboldt, Alexander von (1769-1859)</persName>
    <date>N/A</date>
    <placeName>N/A</placeName>
  </correspAction>
  <correspAction type="received">
    <persName key="H0004321">Lapie, Pierre (1779-1850)</persName>
    <date>N/A</date>
    <placeName>N/A</placeName>
  </correspAction>
</correspDesc>
```

Postal address

The postal address of a letter has been encoded in the opener element (start of the letter) or in the closer (close of the letter). It consists of the address element and one or more addrLine child elements.

```
<opener>
```

```
<address>
  <addrLine>Berlin, Kronenstraße 6</addrLine>
</address>
</opener>
```

Beginning of the letter

The beginning of the letter has been encoded with the `opener` element. Inside, if any, the date and salutation have been encoded with the `dateline` and `salute` elements respectively.

In the `dateline` element the `@rend` attribute has been used if the date is indented or aligned to the right. For example:

```
<opener>
  <dateline rend="align(right)">30 de julio de 1827</dateline>
  <salute>Mi muy apreciable amigo y señor:</salute>
</opener>
```

Writing sessions

The writing sessions have been encoded with the `div` element with two attributes: on the one hand, the `@type` attribute contains the value `writingSession`; on the other hand, `@n` indicates the number of the writing session.

```
<div type="writingSession" n="1">
  <p>[First writing session]</p>
</div>
<div type="writingSession" n="2">
  <p>[Second writing session]</p>
</div>
```

Closing of the letter

The closing of the letter has been encoded in the `closer` element. The salutation formula has been encoded with the `salute` element while the signature has been encoded with the `signed` element. The `@rend` attribute of the `closer` element represents the form or appearance of the closing of the letter.

Value for <code>@rend</code>	Closing letter
paragraph	paragraph
within the line	within the line

For example:

```
<closer rend="paragraph">
  <salute>Muchos saludos</salute>
  <signed>F. E.</signed>
</closer>
```

If there was a date at the close of the letter, it has been encoded in the `closer` element with `dateline`.

```
<closer rend="paragraph">
  <dateline>4 de enero de 1886</dateline>
  <!-- [...] -->
</closer>
```

Postscript

The postscript has been encoded after the closer with the `postscript` element. The postscript always contains at least one paragraph (`p`).

```
<postscript>  
  <p>Para Barón von Humboldt</p>  
</postscript>
```